

Anton Paar Kaomi for Nova

version 1.01
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Report date: 09/04/2025 **Operator:** admin
File Name: AA_TB-pyridine-page141 CO2 273K.qcuPhyslso

Analysis Information

Sample	ID AA_TB-pyridine	Weight 0.14g	Description AA_TB-pyridine-page141 CO:
Analysis	Data ID {e3fd88dc-11b5-4d8d-80f0-aec0d600605f}	Date 2022/05/12	Duration 0.00min
	Operator quantachrome		Firmware 0.00
	Instrument NOVA	Station ID A	Cell ID 79
	Ambient Temp. -273.16°C	p₀ Mode	Thermal Delay 600sec
	Cell Volume 0		
Adsorbate	Name Carbon-dioxide	Molecular Weight 0g/mol	Cross Sectional Area 0 Å ² /molecule
	Non-Ideality 0 _{1/Torr}	Bath Temperature 273.15K	
Degassing	Degas Time 0.0hrs	Degas Temperature 0.0°C	

Data Reduction Parameters

Thermal Transpiration	yes	Eff. Molec. Diameter	3.54Å
Eff. Cell Diameter	4mm		
Adsorbate Model	Name Carbon Dioxide	Molecular Weight 44.0095g/mol	Cross Sectional Area 21 Å ² /molecule
	Bath Temperature 273.15K		

BET Multipoint BET Results

Isotherm Branch	Adsorption
Slope	24.8309
Intercept	0.63648
Correlation coeff., r	0.999533
C constant	40.0128
Surface area	112.832 m ² /g

Table - BET Multipoint BET

Relative Pressure, p/p ₀	Volume Adsorbed @STP cm ³ /g	1 / [W((p ₀ /p) - 1)]
0.0255684	10.5247	1.2697
0.0265798	10.7226	1.2969
0.0274257	10.8973	1.3179
0.0283753	11.0828	1.3420
0.0293415	11.2669	1.3664
0.0303536	11.4597	1.3912
0.0309599	11.6005	1.4027